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Educate."*

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ANDRES “UNDER” BONIFACIO

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A noble being, a paragon admired for his character
Oh! Andres Bonifacio, a hero we revere for being a true model
But what's this? He has become a joke for the street corner idlers
His name is ridiculed, belittled as if he were desperate
They attach "Andress" to "under," followed by Bonifacio

My understanding is unclear, in my young mind it's like a storm
Why was "under" created as if it were a scheme
In a relationship of submission, isn't it not a sign
That agreements and compromise should be valued over hoarse arguments
In a loving marriage, happiness is the reward, with many bonuses

Respect masculinity, understand and proclaim it
The true significance when Mister is postponed
Vices bring joy but only for a moment
Avoid bad company and follows his Misis
Being obedient only leads to a better path

Open your mind and be mature in discussions
Do not degrade others, instead, they should be admired
Bonifacio rests in peace, let him no longer be a target
Of jokes full of laughter but painful when personal
Whether you're single or married, what's important is you hurt no one

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